

Supplementary material: Figures for Appendix D of the paper “Investigating 39 Galactic Wolf-Rayet stars with VLT/GRAVITY: Uncovering a long period binary desert”

Fig. 1. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 8 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 3. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 12 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 2. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 9 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 4. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 14 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 5. [V]-T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 15 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 8. [V]-T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 23 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 6. [V]-T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 16 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 9. [V]-T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 24 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 7. [V]-T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 21 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 10. [V]-T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 31 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 11. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 31a fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 14. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 48 fit with two point sources to model the binary, along with a fully resolved component, and the corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 12. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 42 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 15. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 52 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 13. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 47 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 16. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 55 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 17. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 57 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 20. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 78 fit with only a point source, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 18. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 66 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 21. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 79 fit with a point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 19. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 75 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 22. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 79a fit with an unresolved point source, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 23. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 79b fit with an unresolved point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 26. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 87 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 24. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 81 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 27. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 92 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 25. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 85 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 28. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 93 fit with two point sources to model the binary, along with a fully resolved component, and the corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 35. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 114 fit with a central point source + fully resolved component, along with corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 36. $|V|$ -T3PHI data (top panels) for WR 115 fit with two point sources to model the binary, along with a fully resolved component, and the corresponding residuals (bottom panels).

Fig. 37. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 9 with the best-fit model, similar to Figure 5 in the paper.

Fig. 38. A zoomed-in snippet of complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 16 with the best-fit model, similar to Figure 6 in the paper.

Fig. 39. A zoomed-in snippet of complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 31a with the best-fit model, similar to Figure 6 in the paper.

Fig. 40. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 42 with the best-fit model, similar to Figure 5 in the paper.

Fig. 41. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 47 with an approximate model (similar to Fig. 5 in the paper) over-plotted.

Fig. 42. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 48 with the best-fit binary model.

Fig. 43. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 57 with the best-fit model.

Fig. 44. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 79 with the best-fit model, similar to Figure 5 in the paper.

Fig. 45. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 81 with the best-fit model.

Fig. 46. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 89 with the best-fit binary model.

Fig. 47. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 92 with the best-fit model.

Fig. 48. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 93 with the best-fit binary model.

Fig. 49. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 110 with an approximate model (similar to WR 78) over-plotted.

Fig. 50. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 113 with the best-fit model.

Fig. 51. Complete spectro-interferometric data for WR 115 with the best-fit binary model.